

Resilience: A peer-to-peer wealth redistribution system

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Abstract. A purely peer-to-peer version of wealth redistribution would allow people to coordinate their own taxation without the use of a central government. Such a system would rely instead on redistributing taxes via the peers as trusted intermediaries. The network formed by multi-hop mutual credit payments provides a transport network for peer-to-peer wealth redistribution. Payment paths can be used to transport tax between peers, achieving scalability by "multi-hop routing", the same design philosophy that governs data transmission on the internet.

1. Introduction

Taxation relies almost exclusively on central government serving as trusted third parties to redistribute tax. While the system works well enough for some purposes, it suffers from inherent weaknesses of the coercion-based model that comes with dominance hierarchies. Consent is not acquired, making the tax enforcement a form of theft, and resistance causes friction in coordinating the wealth redistribution. This cost can be avoided with non-coercive taxation, but no mechanism exists to enforce and redistribute taxes in a network without a central trusted party.

What is needed is a wealth redistribution system that is based on horizontal instead of vertical redistribution, avoiding the coercive behaviour that comes with dominance hierarchies. A peer-to-peer routing system for tax would respect free will, and extend rather than amputate. In this paper, we propose a redistribution system using a peer-to-peer transport system that routes taxes via the peers as intermediaries, favouring peers who contribute to the tax pool and bypassing those who do not completely. This peer-to-peer mechanism for redistribution of wealth is fault tolerant, has no central points of control, and scales to infinite size.

2. Trust index

The regulation of tax-rates in a peer-to-peer wealth redistribution system is ideally done with a peer-to-peer selection mechanism. To achieve decentralized regulation of tax-rates, payment pathways are assigned a "bandwidth", governing how efficient they are at transporting taxes. Peers use their bandwidth to compete for the taxes that are transported over the network. The "bandwidth" is defined with the tax applied to a payment, and the tax-rate is decided on by each peer autonomously. Peers compete to transport tax based on the tax-rates they choose.

The “trust index” parameter defines the tax-rate people apply on their payments, regulated autonomously by each individual peer, and payment paths are assigned “bandwidth” based on the tax people choose to apply to their payments, acting as a peer-to-peer selection mechanism for regulating tax-rates within the peer-to-peer wealth redistribution network.

3. Credit network

The selection mechanism is added on top of payment pathways in a multi-hop credit network. Path-based payments takes money down to the smallest possible scale, achieving scalability not by centralizing all account balances under a central bank, but instead by maximally distributing all balances, making each peer their own bank. Peers issue money, and can only do so to other peers who trust them. Payments scale by finding a path of peers that trust one another, going from you to the peer you send the payment to.

Peers keep compartmentalized balances between one another, and receiving a payment from one peer does not change your balance with another peer. The way your balance is cleared is instead via credit clearing, when a circle of debt has formed.

The payment pathways in the multi-hop payment network are what create the “web” that Resilience is built on top of, similar to how email built on top of the internet.

4. Social security

Tax is redistributed by “hopping” from peer to peer along payment paths, analogous to packages of data in TCP/IP, propagating until it reaches a dead end, a peer without an “income” (or with payment pathways from peers who chose to not pay any tax at all.) Tax that reaches a peer without any outgoing links remains with that peer, providing them with guaranteed basic income.

5. Scalability

Computation-wise, the protocol has an infinite capacity. All processes are only ever over a single hop, and tax “packages” can converge at any hop, minimizes computation.

6. Implementation

These types of systems, multi-hop mutual credit and multi-hop wealth redistribution, use isolated, compartmentalized, private exchanges, and do not need a public ledger. This also means they can use perfect secrecy with one-time pad crypto or similar (adding simple MAC to avoid risk of a bit or two being changed in transit.) This gives us a perfect system cryptographically, with much smaller attack surface than a public ledger (as in, no attack surface at all more or less, compared to a public ledger that could never protect itself against brute force other than by being ahead of attackers in key-size.)

References

Fugger, Ryan. (2004). Money as IOUs in Social Trust Networks and a Proposal for a Decentralized Currency Network Protocol. <http://archive.ripple-project.org/decentralizedcurrency.pdf>

Fugger, Ryan. (2006). Payment as a Routing Problem. <http://ripple.ryanfugger.com/paymentrouting.pdf>